

A Lover's Discourse [revisited]

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Abstract

Against the setting of *A Lover's Discourse*, Roland Barthes's romantic compilation of anxious and blissful literary (and spoken) expressions of love, I propose to discuss instances of potential 'lover talk' analyzing them in terms of emotive evocation and semantics. The examples to be examined are of two kinds: an advertising billboard, containing a verbal message, and a traditional handcrafted artifact, containing a subtle message of persuasion in its design. The Zulu [one of South Africa's indigenous ethnic groups] have a rich oral narrative tradition which translates into visual form in the case of the handcrafted necklace pieces which lovers send to each other, appropriately called 'love letters'. In another realm of South African life, daring advertising billboards stake territory on street sides, and the perceiver from another culture is moved by the content of the message.

The advertising billboard and a handmade necklace are far-removed from literary discourse (or are they?) but are worth examining because of the emotions they evoke through metonymy and symbolism. One contains a spelled out proposition presented graphically; the other supposedly contains a message that is not decipherable in the habitual code of written or spoken word.

In discussing these two instances, I wish to kindle thought about the emotive aspects of such culturally, hierarchically, and spatially diverse approaches to communication: one, a public large-scale proclamation, directed at the literate perceiver-consumer, the other, a token of private "writing".

The discourse represented in the billboard befits the solitude Barthes discusses. It is, however, *reported* discourse from the part of the lover's object, but all the same unwarranted and uncalled for, and definitely not personable, or genuine. It is not intimate, but it warrants no response, whereas the Zulu necklace, artsy and personal, represents a mechanism tied up in old traditions and authority, and refers to a conventional and demarcated interaction in a social group. ". The mutual affinity of these 'discourses' and their affinity to the theme of emotion, are discussed. Has the lover's discourse "...no recourse, but to become the site, however exiguous, of an *affirmation*."? *

*Roland Barthes: *A Lover's Discourse: Fragments*.

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To put you in amorous mood, I propose to you a passage from Goethe's Werther:
"I am living through days as happy as those God keeps for his chosen people, and whatever becomes of me, I can never say that I have not tasted the purest joys of life". (Barthes, 1978)

As discourse is interaction in language, spoken and written, it is also a social construct (Kress and van Leeuwen, 2001; Barthes, 1967) and a convention of symbols and metaphors. Therefore, the signification of semantic discourse is a signification more broadly, a signification of a culture. A Lover's Discourse, a compilation of anxious and blissful "fragments" of love talk (Barthes, 1978), gave me a starting point, to approach the topic of emotion – and for the purposes of the conference theme at hand – the topics of emotion AND design. I therefore propose to discuss love - or a potentiality of love - and the semantics of love, in two visual instances: a traditional Zulu artifact made of beads, called "a love letter", and a Clear Channel (™) advertising billboard spotted along a street side in Pretoria, where billboards are ubiquitous.

At first glance, the two examples seem a strange pair: after all, the only criterion suggesting their likeness, and the affinity to the category of lover's discourse, is the word 'love': the Zulu necklace is called 'a love letter', and the billboard, in its textual content appears to discuss love. What do they have in common, what is dissimilar? To what degree do they each constitute emotional discourse, and in what ways are their semantic qualities evocative of emotion?

Both of the designed objects under investigation are in the South African ethnosphere where I am now living. The billboard directed at a mass audience and the traditional, indigenous love letter necklace are clearly representative of the South African cultural frame of mind. Neither item displays an avoidance of emotion; in fact, they are saturated with it. Both, at least superficially, deal with love. Does the affinity of the two end with this word as their subject matter?

Figure 1: Billboard in Pretoria, South Africa, photographed by Maarit Tevanlinna-Alvarez, October 2005

It was my aim to find out the significations of the love letter and the billboard, which can be read in the habitual code of English, and examined visually. For this, I presented a picture and two modifications I had prepared of the billboard, to focus group informants of young University of Pretoria students. I collected their reactions. I had a second focus group, much more informally assembled, consisting of employees at a bookshop in Pretoria. In passing, both groups looked at pictures of Zulu love letters, and it soon became evident that they were not familiar with the signification of the love letter, even though all of the university student informants were from the indigenous tribal backgrounds. In fact, they did not know the rather charming English name of such an artifact. Moreover, they were eager to articulate upon the billboard, which evoked discussion on the topics of advertising, ethics, segregation, education, literacy and others. As for the love letter, I relied largely on literary sources, which were few, although I also interviewed Mr. Dlomo, at the African languages department of

University of Pretoria. Mr. Dlomo was interviewed through an interpreter, as he is not literate in English. Contrary to the other interviewees, who have either graduated or are studying at a university, Mr. Dlomo, despite his post at the University, has not completed the secondary education. He teaches Zulu articulation to non-Zulu language students. Mr. Dlomo was shown both images of love letters in literature as well as the picture of the advertising billboard.

The instances exemplified are described in my paper, with the help of these focus group interviews, and analyzed and compared against the backdrop of Roland Barthes's 'discourse'.

Positioning of the billboard

The billboard was on display for about five months, from October 2005 to March 15, 2006 - quite a stint for advertisements, which are usually very ephemeral. Another one, advertising Honda cars, then replaced it. It stands on a park-like piece of land at a four-way crossing, near the University of Pretoria, isolated and without interference from visual competitors in its category. Enumerating the parts of the ensemble, it is noted that the advertisement consists of a sentence of two phrases - /we had...once/ and /he said he loved me/ - and a picture of a bottle, on a white background. The sentence 'WE HAD ONCE AND HE SAID HE LOVED ME' is pierced vertically, between the words /had/ and /once/ by a pictorial element, a bottle, which clearly occupies a position of a missing lexical item. The bottle in this composition is observed first, and the sentence follows, meshed with the picture: first the paradigmatic, selective, metaphoric, then the syntagmatic, combinatory, and metonymic (Jakobson: 1990). The words are all monosyllables, contrary to the word spelled on the label of the bottle, which is rotated 90 degrees: *appletiser*.

It is a palpable message, there is no subtlety in it: whoever is speaking "We had once..." is charmed, and I, as the viewer, am charmed secondarily, by the potentiality of a love proclamation. There is a memory of an event before this moment, the instance of "once". It is evocative of something that appeals to my senses. "It is a female", comments one of the informants, "speaking to a friend of what has happened earlier, maybe last night". Moreover, "it denotes a celebration", and "a nice memory". Another one agrees adding: "Ladies like to gossip." It is a grammatically valid sentence. It does not seem awkward in the way of the

Chomskyan “Colorless green dreams sleep furiously”, quoted by Jacob Mey (Mey:1993). However, conjoined these phrases - /we had...once/ and /he said he loved me/ - seem implausible, and ambiguous, as there is no knowing, whether *we* of the first phrase denotes at all the *he* and *me* of the latter phrase. In its narration, it remains open for interpretations. The two phrases /we had...once/ and /he said he loved me/ are joined by a conjunction ‘and’. Is there a deduction here, as in logic? Is the /we had...once/ a cause to /he said he loved me/? “No” says one of the interviewees, “it was happening at the same time, in the process of happening he said he loved me.” He added that it was an utterance that one would be expected to be “actively involved in; they want you to connect it to something, asking basically to bring in all your senses.” It is a speech act coined by an advertising copywriter, ambiguous and implicit, even naïve.

Pragmatics of the necklace

Though once ritual objects of immediacy, the traditional Zulu bead crafts nowadays are relics housed in museum displays; they are therefore fittingly Barthesian: forsaken and exiguous. The love letter is a necklace, a craft object made by a woman in a tribal setting, who has the understanding of the social demarcation, a kind of tacit knowledge. The true love letters date from before 1960, before the establishment of the *apartheid* (Morris, 45), when Zulu men would go to Durban (Thekwini, meaning "The Place Where the Earth and the Ocean Meet" or Johannesburg (Egoli, “the Place of Gold”), to work in the mines, returning home infrequently. The women would make intricate necklaces for their men, with the centerpiece of the necklace falling into the hollow of the neck. This was always one-way messaging: men did not engage in the necklace discourse, and for women, too, this was the only way of courting or otherwise engaging a man – it was never the woman’s place to approach a man except obliquely: never directly but by dispatching a delicate cue or suggestion. In the patterning of the necklaces, one would give a cue such as “I really want to tell you my feelings about the present situation”. Sometimes, marriage-age girls could make and send to one object of affection their rival necklaces.

Figure 2: Examples of *ucu* neck ornaments from Nongoma area, Kwazulu-Natal Province, South Africa. Morris, Jean: *Speaking with Beads. Zulu arts from Southern Africa*, 1994. Photography by Eleanor Preston-Whyte. Thames and Hudson.

The love letter is private, small, decorative, an appeal for coaxing to take measures. The colors of the beads bear meanings, negative and positive, and so does their arrangement in the flat piece: the code in them, however vernacular or idiolectic, may even be a convention of a single man and a woman. In some cases - my informant Mr. Dlomo tells me - the full meaning of the rhetoric of a necklace would only reveal itself as the recipient arrived and was given a closer explanation of it. Love letters could similarly, merely fulfill the task of a decoration, an adornment with the patterns varying from area to area. Pondering the changing times, Mr. Dlomo says that nowadays girls – and it was girls who’d make the bead decorations – won’t even know how to build a house, let alone arrange beads! In Zulu culture, the house building was women’s work – men would be away, at the king’s court, in battles or tending to the wealth of cattle.

The semantics of the beads

Until I knew of the hidden messages in the necklace, I would only examine it based on its aesthetic qualities: its color composition and pattern, and marvel at the skillful sewing together of the tiny beads. Now, it would also appeal to me by its mythical, exotic, and romantic meanings.

It is noted that the literature on the Zulu beadwork eloquently describes it in the terminology of language attesting it is likened to language: “...there is freedom....but also discipline to a degree approaching the demands of grammatical prescription.” “The Zulu practice their art with an intuitive fluidity usually found only in the more inspirational forms of visual art and poetry” but “... meaning is often obscured by the wealth of proverbs and imagery.” (Schoeman: 1993).

Over the years, new fashions of geometric and color schemes have replaced the original beadwork with designerly and desired patterns... (Morris:1994) No longer will the designs contain messages of courtship and marriage, such as: “My heart bleeds for you, when will you come for me?”

The central constant symbol of the necklace is the triangle; with the apex facing up it denotes the subject: a marriageable woman, while the apex down denotes the similar male principle, an unmarried man. Combined these form a diamond shape representing a complete feminine principle, a married woman. The signification of the apexes meeting: a married man.

White, the color of purity, is the only color without the dichotomous negative-positive values of the other colors, whose meanings are changing to the degree that their meaning, negative or positive is obscured and reversed at will. The “bleeding heart” can just as well be “a happy heart”. (Schoeman: 1983). The primary male symbol, the triangle pointing down, may not be placed within the female triangle, even if the subject wished to express herself as being in love; her red female symbol, on the contrary must be placed within the primary male symbol.

Flavor, purity and the male principle

In what ways are the semantic qualities in the love letter and the billboard, evocative of emotion, from the points of view of language, design and culture? Roman Jakobson’s selection of six functions of language, each according to the participant of a communication event, includes the emotive or expressive function; its focus is on the addresser, and its “aims a direct expression of the speaker’s attitude toward what he is speaking about”. It tends to, according to Jakobson “produce an impression of a certain emotion, whether true or feigned”. Jakobson points out that the emotive function tends to “flavor all our utterances, on their phonic, grammatical and lexical level”. (Jakobson, 1990). This flavor of emotion enters in the form of metaphors, the lexical items that can be substituted by others, on a paradigmatic or similarity axle of a language event. (Jakobson, 1990).

The sentence of the billboard is placed quietly on a white background, in one single string of serif typeface, black and in all capitals. Near the top of the pictured bottle, there is a green asterisk: then the caption of the asterisk, down, in the bottom right: *100% Pure Pleasure*. The words are spelled with initial capitals, one-hundred-per-cent in numerical form. What does such absolute pure pleasure exemplify: real juice, purity of heart, naturalness? The drink is pure, real, and this might indicate that the lover’s words are pure and genuine, adhering to the purity concept, says one observer.

Assuming that the /me/ in the billboard's discourse is a female, and that /we/ denotes both her, the speaker, and "him" of /he said/, we get a "report" of an event of one kind, related by the female. The speech event could have alternatively been: "We had *appletiser* once and I said I loved her", as one of my modifications of the text proposes. Were the phrases rearranged to this form, however, a different perspective would come to play: one informant observed that the declaration of love, uttered by a male, would not be as emotional as reported by the female. Where emotion is involved, the female reporting this is positively emotional, whereas a male speaker's: "...I said I loved her" would arouse negative emotion. "It [would sound like] a regret", says one informant.

Pure Pleasure is a reference ambiguous to purity, natural quality of the juice or the connection with relaxation, good times which accompany having this very brand of a drink. As some of my informants suggest, this 'purity' is similar to one produced by the washing powder SKIP, which makes everything white, one marketed more in the city; the powder OMO makes the "colored clothes more colorful, more brilliant", [as there is more color in the rural areas]. This, my informants assure me, is not analogous to racial black-white segregation. The billboard use of color is very sparing; it is sleek and "clean".

The image of a bottle is more meaningful than the text, which does not "open" to a rural dweller. The narrative, if you will, is redundant in this case. It is public, urban, commercial, and segregated.

Under further scrutiny, the billboard draws attention with the fact that the words on it are all monosyllables, all but *appletiser*. One cannot help but try to figure out what the bottle replaces: the cues are there; the rest of the lexical items are monosyllables, should the metaphor be, too? We had fun once and he said he loved me. We had tea once and he said he loved me. *We had sex once and....* Further: is the first phrase the cause or the effect? Was the blank the cause of the love proclamation? Whether the cause or the effect, it was not a five rand one-liter soda but an eleven rand 750 ml one-hundred-per-cent pure pleasure.

The demarcations of the bead designs and the sanctions of the triangles enclosing each other, which was discussed above, could be mirrored in the billboard: the male's presence, 'the male

principle' is enclosed in the female discourse, however. It is reported: he said he loved me. It is speech within speech: overlapping messages.

Sweet-talking of the narrative

“When it comes to getting something from a woman...the whole world knows...that for you to get something from a woman you need to sweet-talk them, buy them this...buy them that... I believe that for you to get something out of a woman, if you can make her love, that is sweet talking anyway...buying her stuff,” says a person in the bookstore.

It is conceivable, I am told, that a township fellow would buy an *appletiser* to offer to the girl, even if it is not available at the local “bottle store”. Such lavishness would show that there might be other material things to come, and that he would be a good provider with means to buy expensive gifts. Then again, my informants tell me, in the townships and in rural areas, this drink is not even available, it is too expensive to buy: people drink beer and *coke* there. “This [*appletiser*] is the kind of drink corporate people would have at a business meeting, mixing with “scotch whisky and brandy”, one informant says.

Mr. Dlomo, who told me about the vernacular of the necklace ‘talk’, thought that the billboard text shows that the speaker [woman] cannot be ‘straight’, and is a “loose woman” uttering a thing like that. “It doesn’t matter who bought her what, but this woman is not ‘straight’.

Mr. Dlomo does not read English, and looked at the billboard picture keenly listening to the interpreter. “It is bad: you can’t say this to a woman... buy her a drink and then assume that she will love you...because you bought her anything...it is morally incorrect”, Mr. Dlomo said, continuing about the counterpart in the narrative: “It won’t be true...it won’t be a good guy. He is buying love”.

Affinity

What do the “we-had-once” and the love letter have in common if anything, once juxtaposed? Do they have something, against the backdrop of Barthes “fragments”, to contribute to design-and-emotion talk? They have an affinity in representing verbal messages, each in its

particular code. Yet, in their semantics and as pragmatic speech acts, they could not be further from each other; the billboard does not “speak” to an uneducated person any more than the love letter speaks to an educated city person. Perceivers of each ‘message’ are from social groups far removed from each other. The affinity between these two instances is problematic due to a prevailing gap between social groups, perhaps compounded by illiteracy and taboos; as the love letter is foreign to the more educated perceiver of the population, so is the advertising billboard to one of the “underprivileged” background. The multilayered marketing message remains enigmatic to an uneducated individual, toiling with the every-day mundane: commuting to and from a job in the city in crowded buses and kombi-taxis to work in shops, or as housekeepers and gardeners in the affluent areas of the city.

The exoticism of the two examples, in fact, reveals that they are outrageously dissimilar. They were conceived worlds apart, and times apart. They are reciprocally mysterious, one a secret for the audience of the other: the necklace and its code to the white European, the billboard and its mechanism to the tribal individual, with its demands for deciphering symbols and its presupposition of the competence in the English language.

Some of the dichotomies between the we-had-once and the love letter may be:

direct message – oblique message;
public – private;
having sensual content – having functional content;
urban - rural;
educated - uneducated;
textual – pictorial;
direct persuasion - oblique persuasion ;
commercial – noncommercial;
not exotic - exotic;
blatant – subtle;
known – unknown;
prosaic – poetic;

But the two instances share the following:

discourse is female, it is one-way, and it is persuasive.

What is my understanding of the we-had-once and the necklace in the cultural context? The message of the bead artwork will remain foreign to me: even if its messages are not of the habitual code of language – which in turn, in the case of Zulu is foreign to me – I will be denied familiarity of that discourse. I understand the billboard, as I can read it, with the help of my language competence, as well as analyze it syntactically and semantically; it is assumed that its designs are based on careful and thorough market place investigations, reinforced by clientele opinion polls, brand makers expertise and calculations to maximize sales. Moreover, its message is ambiguous, and arouses in me an adverse feeling: of falseness, even repulsion, even though its language may include significations that are imbedded deeper in the past of the cultures than I can grasp. It therefore remains equally enigmatic to me as the love letter. The intimacy of a fleeting emotion, a memory, a statement, a lonely thought verbalized by some fictitious mouth, whose origins are in another time, is conveying a Western style sales pitch, as exiguous, as the fragments of Barthes.

In the prologue of *A Lover's Discourse*, Roland Barthes laments that the lover's discourse "today is of an extreme solitude, warranted by no-one...completely forsaken by the surrounding languages...severed not only from authority but also from the mechanisms of authority (sciences, techniques and arts)." Through the "actions of a primary language", the speaking lover is to be reinstated from a "simple symptomal subject" to "the fundamental person, the I, in order to stage an utterance, not an analysis." The fragments exemplifying lovers' discourse presented are not metalanguage, or psychological portraits but the subjects' true utterances, "turnings here and there", genuine and true, even if derided to the degree on being invalid, and not to be reckoned with. (Barthes, 1978).

In conclusion

I have attempted to shed light with the two instances examined, to the discourse of emotion – and in this occasion – design and emotion, the foundations of giving shape and substance. The two instances brought together exemplify what they appeared to have in common: discourse of emotion of love. I have tried to establish the degree of affinity of the two discourses –

temporally and spatially: one ephemeral, the other timeless; one large-scale, the other small; one blatantly commercial in nature, the other private. Both discourses “speak” emotions, and I have found the discourses to be fittingly Barthesian affirmations - solitary, and derided, exiled from gregariness, “severed not only from authority but also from the mechanisms of authority (sciences, techniques, arts).” (Barthes, 1978).

They lack the reciprocal dialogue from the part of the object, which is absent.

In the fashion of the lover’s discourse, the emotive expression, “runnings here and there” (discursus), in instances of art and design talk, too, remain just that: figures “ignored, disparaged”, as well as “forsaken by the surrounding languages (sciences, techniques and arts)”, to borrow Barthes. Such discourse, which flows from spontaneity, tacit knowledge, and intuitive gut-feeling, warrants no reciprocation and has no validity in those other languages: in art and design research, too, a demand for exact episteme hovers, a demand for data, onto which artistic research can be based. The “mechanisms of authority” determine and sanction the discourse and declare which of it is valid, and the rest remains “exiguous affirmations”, void of authority.

In the fashion of a lover’s discourse, the spontaneous and passionate figures, outbursts of language, emotional discourse of creative minds, must similarly be made valid, must similarly be reckoned with. Room must be allocated to creative affirmations, which flow from gut feeling, to figures of a subjective thinker, who is often solitary. It is my understanding that similarly subjective, solitary and passionate style of discourse, replete with emotion, can serve as basis to good of design; it can serve in addressing methods and tools, to give rise to great design.

Epilogue

To leave you with an affirmation of love, befitting to the thought of a daring subjective but frank and sincere discourse, I give you an excerpt from Tatiana’s letter to Onegin, (Pushkin, 1823) in the epic poem “Yevgeny Onegin”:

But so be it! My fate
henceforth I place into your hands,
before you I shed tears,
for your defense I plead.
Imagine: I am here alone,
none understands me,
my reason sinks,
and, silent, I must perish.
I wait for you: revive
my heart's hopes with a single look
or interrupt the heavy dream
with a rebuke--alas, deserved!

I close. I dread to read this over.
I'm faint with shame and fear... But to me
your honor is a pledge,
and boldly I entrust myself to it.

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